

YOSH CHET TILI O'RGANUVCHILARINI AJOYIB USULLAR BILAN SAMARALI O'QITISH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi kunda chet tillarini o'rganish odamlar orasida keng tarqalgan. Ayniqsa, 7 yoshdan 15 yoshgacha bo'lgan yoshlar o'rtasida. Biroq, bu o'rganuvchilar yaxshi ma'lumotli yoki boshqa tomondan muhim usullarni to'g'ri qo'llashni yaxshi bilmaydigan o'qituvchilarga duch kelishadi. Oxir-oqibat, o'quvchilar yangi til o'rganishni zerikarli va foydasiz hisoblab, vaqtlarini behuda sarflayotganlarini tushunishadi. Shunday qilib, ushbu maqola o'qitish va qoniqarli natijalarga erishishning eng muhim usullariga qaratiladi

Kalit so'zlar: strategiyalar, kartalar, Wordwall, Kahoot!, Baamboozle, rol o'yinlari, o'ziga ishonch.

TEACHING YOUNG FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS EFFECTIVELY WITH AMAZING METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays learning foreign languages is widespread among people. Especially, from 7 to 15 years old youth. However, these students are facing with teachers who may be well – educated or on the other hand, are not good at using essential methods in the right way. In the end, pupils are having boring and useless and wasting their time. So this article is going to focus on the most important ways of teaching and getting satisfactory results

Key words: strategies, flashcards, Wordwall, Kahoot!, Baamboozle, role plays, self- confidence, torchbearers.

Main body: There is along and challenging process on the way of absorbing new language. Sometimes teachers are not lucky to choose the right method for their students. And this happens because of variety of them. In fact, every child has his characteristics. In addition, their ways of acquiring information may differ from each other.

Always remember to adapt your teaching strategy to the requirements and interests of your pupils. Also, pupils have a better chance of succeeding if they have the correct motivation for learning English. Therefore, in order to select the ideal approach for teaching English to adults or kids, it is important to first comprehend why a person needs or wants to learn the language before concentrating on the most effective strategy to accomplish that aim.

So far a big circle of strategies, theories or ways have been practiced in order to be good for both sides, teachers and learners. However, not all of them worked as they were expected. As it mentioned above, it depends on learners.

Fortunately, some of them that are going to be mentioned below, have been found convenient for using:

1. Keeping the language simple

This is very important for teachers who are teaching or have intention to do. Because, most of them are building walls between students and new language telling challenges that they will confront with or choosing wrong way for their pupils to be the part of the new world. So when they are in the process of having class, they should try to use repetition. They should be builders of language awareness for beginners. In order not to make them confuse, teachers should be careful while teaching something new by making the language simple.

2. Being fun and dramatic

When it comes to introduce new vocabulary, bringing objects or flashcards would be very helpful. Moreover, being energetic is also one way of catching the attention of them. For example, while animals are being introduced, for some of them being scared or brave, sustain a class with emotional understanding and memorizing the words well.

3. Games and activities

Preparing variety of games or activities which are relevant to the theme.

Children always want to do extraordinary things. Because they are considered as they are often bored and doing the same thing over and over again make their intentions lose. So in order not to have this kind of situations, nowadays for the luck of teachers, there are a lot of games which are online or others, activities have been made. For instance, Wordwall, Kahoot!, Baamboozle. They are online game makers which are being used by dozens and dozens of educationalists.

4. Making children watch cartoons or movies

By doing it , teachers will be able to make their pupils adjust the new language. In fact , each language is learnt by culture and movies and cartoons have the messages about culture to develop. It will make the way easy for learners. And also it will be helpful the skill of listening to increase.

5. Learning by heart poems or songs

If teachers want their students to speak fluently or start speaking , poems, songs , sentences or texts are enough to get this aim. Fortunately , at the moment books which are for new starters of a language have songs or something that are appropriate the theme to learn by heart. For example, Way Ahead books are amazing books to use. Teachers who are using them , will definitely achieve their pupils have sufficient education.

6. Organizing role plays among class.

This is one of the important methods. Because , it gives a big opportunity for language learners to develop or having courage or self- confidence. Generally , role plays are played in front of others , and participants of them will have chance to show off and breaking their hesitation towards their future fear about conversations with native speakers of the language they are learning. They can imagine themselves as they are conversing with natives.

A civilized society's torchbearers are its teachers. Teachers have long used a variety of techniques, strategies, and teaching philosophies to best meet the needs of each student. It is difficult to teach English as a second language to non-native speakers because different strategies must be developed. Given that we are multilingual and have a different socioeconomic background, teaching English should be studied in the right way everywhere.

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